

PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF FORMING A SENSE OF MILITARY PATRIOTISM IN YOUNG PEOPLE BASED ON HEROIC IDEALS

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Abstract: In the article, the theoretical and methodological foundations of the formation of ideals of military heroism in the thinking of young people, the socio-philosophical foundations of the formation of ideals of military heroism in the thinking of young people are studied. Also, philosophical aspects of forming a sense of military patriotism in young people based on heroic ideals are analyzed.

Key words: thinking, patriotism, idealism, phenomenon, rational, heroism, military heroism, historical, military courage, pride, national, philosophical, patriotism, moral, education.

INTRODUCTION. Formation of a sense of military patriotism in young people based on heroic ideals is a feeling that shows high morality, and its meaning is strengthened by direct and indirect responsibility for love of the motherland, protection of the motherland, ensuring its safety and integrity. That is why true military patriotism demands that he put his family above family, Motherland above family, and humanity above Motherland. According to these scientists, the important aspect of virtue is that its qualities do not fit into the narrow circle of patriotism, they "go beyond" it. Military patriotism is not limited to loving or loving the Motherland, but it is manifested in mobilizing all strength and intelligence to solve problems related to the protection of the Motherland.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. In the spiritual heritage created by mankind, ideas about heroism are found in mythological, religious-didactic, epic works such as the Avesta, Tripitaka, Ramayana, Mahabharata, Iliad, Alpomish, divine books such as the Torah, Psalms, Bible, Qur'an, hadiths and it is found in the examples of our classical literature, in the works of many philosophers. Problems of the impact of scientific research on historical and moral ideals on youth education R.Michner, S.Kautz, J.Sitser, Fernand Grenand, Frederic Starr, Eiji Mano, Magida Mahluf, Mark Bonnell, Yul Janssens, Masataka Takeshita, Shi Yunli, P. Petrov, S.I. Tyulyayev, S.P. Tolstov, K. Pirliyev, R.R. Safin, I.F. Kharlamov, B. Toychiyev, I. Inoyatov, M. Abilov, V. Kaloshin, O. Abdurasulov, A. Sa'diyev . .Komilov, U. Mansur, U. Mahkamov, S. Nishonova, N. Artikov, O. Musurmonova, K. Qilichevalar.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. At present, the basis of military patriotism is the peace of the country. In today's dangerous times, increasing the power of our Armed Forces, deepening the processes of modernization of our national army, strengthening our country's defense capabilities, protecting the integrity of our homeland's borders is the main condition and guarantee of this methodology. The ethical nature of this condition requires the following aspects:

1. Moral consciousness of military personnel. It consists of a system of moral concepts, ideas, views, beliefs, and feelings that correspond to the interests of service teams, which is reflected in their behavior in society, in everyday life, and in service activities. These are feelings of love for the Motherland, devotion to duty, responsibility to society, national pride and pride.

2. Ethics of military personnel. This is patriotism, bravery, knowing the most modern weapons and tools, being able to use them in any situation, being faithful to the rules of combat comradeship and not leaving the battlefield, being faithful to the military oath and doing military duty until the last minute of life. It is characterized by the performance. The above principles require that military patriotism should become a characteristic characteristic of young people who deeply respect the history and destiny of the motherland, people, and are able to show examples of selflessness in the interests of the Motherland. Because, only when love for the Motherland and trust in its future are formed on the basis of a single goal aimed at the interests of the whole nation, military patriotism becomes a virtue of all those who connect their fate with the fate of the Motherland and the nation. Therefore, the virtue of military patriotism requires everyone to take responsibility for their work, preserve and protect the Motherland, strive to maintain peace, stability and tranquility in the country, and put the interests of the Motherland and the nation first in international relations.

In our opinion, it is necessary to analyze the moral values of everyday military activity in order to visualize military patriotism more clearly. Among such virtues are the following patriotism, duty, responsibility, military honor, pride, humanitarianism, kindness, brotherhood, faith, nobility, perseverance, dedication, conscientiousness, performance, responsibility, independence, obedience, , enthusiasm, altruism, integrity, truthfulness, professionalism, justice, awareness, diligence, sincerity and other positive aspects.

Military moral values include bravery, bravery, fearlessness, heroism, bravery, strength, ambition, bravery, endurance, bravery and other positive aspects. Limitation of the moral values of military activity is considered

conditional according to its manifestation on the main fronts, therefore these moral values in reality are absorbed into the entire military activity with the participation of different sides of the single process.

It should be noted that military patriotism is connected to the ancient history and spiritual sources of our national heritage. For example, military patriotism in the literary monument "Avesta", in heroic epics such as "Go'rog'li", "Alpomish", "Tuzuklari Temur", "Mahbub ul-Qulub", "Turkiy gulistan yahud akhloq" it is extremely relevant to study issues related to the promotion of ideas in the context of ethics. Because the formation of moral qualities such as pride, honor, honor, trust and loyalty in young people becomes a reality based on the conditions of military patriotism.

In addition, it is important for young people to glorify the military patriotism of our grandfathers like Spitamen, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Najmuddin Kubro, Temur Malik, Amir Temur, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur as a moral ideal, and to analyze the sources that reflect their moral views and life activities related to the virtue of patriotism. serves to increase military patriotism.

It should be noted that in the moral values of the Uzbek people, military patriotism is valued as a characteristic characteristic of individuals who are able to show examples of selflessness in the defense of the Motherland, looking at the country's history and fate with deep respect. This feeling is formed on the basis of moral concepts such as "love", "trust", "loyalty" and is a philosophical category that has not lost its status over the years because it has taken a deep place in the hearts of people. Patriotism is glorified in all sources related to the spiritual heritage of the Uzbek people, as it embodies moral qualities such as unification, orientation, cohesion, and mobilization.

In all periods of human history, state troops have been its support, a pledge of peace and tranquility of the people. The issues of the state of the troops, their supply, and the responsibility, courage and loyalty of the military in the performance of their duties, as well as the spiritual and moral aspects, have become important in the development of the countries. In this regard, the opinions of the scholars of the East regarding the formation of high moral and ethical qualities in the army, in particular, the commander and the soldiers, are noteworthy. In particular, Abu Nasr Farabi puts forward advanced ideas about the army chief and his qualities. In his opinion, along with useful and beautiful intellectual abilities, the army chief should also have moral qualities common to all soldiers. If he wants to finish these actions, he will use qualities characteristic of soldiers. His bravery should match the bravery shown in the individual

actions of the military. According to Farabi, the qualities characteristic of the army include such high human qualities as wisdom, judgment, persuasiveness, physical strength, mental freshness, spiritual maturity, patriotism, and courage. Because without these, the army cannot be perfect and victorious. Alloma's ideas were developed by later thinkers.

Our spiritual heritage of military patriotism teaches that in war against the enemy, the ruler and the army must follow the rules of justice: this ensures the inevitable victory over the enemy. For this, the ruler must be capable, far-sighted, and in a certain sense, have the art of "espionage". In this regard, Jalaluddin Davani emphasizes that soldiers should have 3 qualities. These are a) courage, b) intelligence, c) skill. For example, it is important to properly evaluate and encourage soldiers who have shown themselves in battle. It is not proper for a king to lose his vigilance even after defeating an enemy. He must keep the country's military power secret from the enemy. According to Davani, soldiers are the most courageous people because they guard the borders and fortresses of the state. Therefore, they are considered the most respected people of the state. The head of state should always provide them with material support and honor every soldier.

The ideas of the enlightener Ahmad Donish about the military leader, their qualities and their attitude to their subordinates are valuable. Alloma says that the head of the army must have such qualities as courage, understanding, experience, courage, intelligence, wisdom, and bravery. A person with such qualities becomes a soldier's leader, only then he will save the soldier, not leave him to harm and trouble, and win glory and honor by defeating the enemy. Therefore, Eastern thinkers focused their attention on the one hand, on increasing the strength of the troops, improving their military skills, maintaining the integrity and security of the country, and on the other hand, on educating the moral, moral and ideological qualities of the army. Today, these opinions of our scholars will undoubtedly be an important source for strengthening the military potential of our country, increasing the combat readiness of military personnel, and educating them with high human qualities.

Military patriotism education is the ability and readiness of the citizens of Uzbekistan to bravely defend our Motherland, the spiritual and moral system of educating soldiers in the spirit of patriotism. This form of education sets the following main tasks for the formation of military patriotism:

- to strengthen the feeling of love for the Motherland in military personnel;

- to create a sense of responsibility in the defense of the country and strengthening the combat power of the armed forces of the state;
- forming a sense of determination and loyalty to the country.

Researcher G.M. Ergasheva explains that military patriotism education differs from general patriotism in a number of ways:

- firstly, military patriotism aims to prepare citizens of Uzbekistan to defend the Motherland with weapons;
- secondly, the basis of military patriotism is formed by the achievements of the Armed Forces of Uzbekistan, and the basis of patriotism education is formed by military achievements along with labor achievements;
- thirdly, education of military patriotism instills a sense of respect and pride towards the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the desire and aspiration to become a military serviceman and defend the independent homeland with a weapon in hand. Patriotic education develops the feeling of loyalty to the Motherland, the strengthening of the greatness and strength of the country, and the protection of the independence of the citizen of Uzbekistan. In this sense, it can be said that patriotic education of military personnel is a systematic and purposeful activity of military administration bodies and officials. A military serviceman is always required to be ready for this activity.

CONCLUSION. The essence of the ethics of military service, its main concepts and characteristics, the moral foundations of military service and scientific and educational sources related to the issues of moral education in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan., it is noted that he is distinguished by his ability to apply in any conditions, to be loyal to the rules of combat comradeship, not to leave the battlefield, to remain loyal to the Military Oath, and to fulfill his military duty until the last moments of his life. Also, the moral rules of military personnel are expressed in the Military Oath and General Military Regulations. The role of the morals of military personnel in the development of society is determined by creating all-round conditions for the peaceful living of the inhabitants of this country, that is, by protecting them from external threats - enemy aggression.

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